

Essential role of chemoinformatics in chemistry

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Introduction

Chemoinformatics is the application of informatics methods to solve chemical problems. This discipline slowly evolved and was never formally installed. In order to apply informatics methods to Chemistry, we have to first understand the fundamental problems of chemists. A primary job of a chemist is to synthesize compounds with desired properties. However, the properties of compounds are dependent on their structures, therefore the fundamental task of a chemist is to make inference about the structure-property/activity relationship. This domain of chemistry when assessed in quantitative manner is known as **Quantitative Structure-Property or Quantitative Structure-Activity relationship (QSPR or QSAR)** (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1a. Structure-property/activity relationships.

Next challenge for a chemist is to synthesize the desired molecule by a chemical reaction or sequence of reactions starting from available materials. This is the domain of **chemical synthesis design** (Fig. 1b).

Fig. 1b. Design of reaction/sequence of reactions to make a given structure from available materials.

The third important task for a chemist is to ascertain the structure and purity of the synthesized molecule, since the chemical reactions do not

always take the expected route and side reactions may also occur. This is the domain of **structural elucidation** which includes the application of chromatographic and spectral tools. A number of spectroscopic techniques viz. UV, IR, NMR and Mass spectra are applied.

Fig. 1c. Structure elucidation.

All the three tasks are quite complicated and cannot be achieved without the help of prior information, which is available in the form of knowledge. The amount of information which has to be processed is very large. More than 45 million compounds are known, each having different physical, chemical and biological properties as well as different methods of preparation and characterized by a host of spectra. This plethora of information can be assessed only through electronic means i.e. by use of computers. Here comes the need for Chemoinformatics.

The scope of chemoinformatics

In mid sixties scientists started feeling that the vast information collected in Chemistry has to be saved in electronic form i.e. in data bases, in order to make it accessible to the scientific community. A new field was emerging dealing with the storage, processing and manipulation of the chemical data without a proper name. In 1973 a summer school with the title, "Computer Representation and Manipulation of Chemical information" was held at NATO Advanced Study Institute in Netherlands, which brought together all scientists working in different areas of chemistry but dealing with application of computers to manage chemical information. The scientists attending this summer school worked on building chemical structure databases, developed different softwares i.e. for organic synthesis design, analyzing spectral data and for Chemometrics. This was the emergence of a new field which had applications in many areas of Chemistry. Suddenly the change was evident since in 1975, the "Journal of Chemical Documentation" changed its name to "Journal of Chemical Information and Computer Science". The scientists working in this field called it "Computer Chemistry" but since the term could be confused with "Computational Chemistry" which is more

confined to the study of theoretical quantum mechanical calculations, the term “Chemoinformatics” was coined. This is sometimes spelt as “Cheminformatics”, but the former spellings are more commonly used. The following broad definition has been given to this new emerging interdisciplinary field by Paris¹ in the meeting of American Chemical Society in August 1999,

“Chem(o)informatics is a generic term that encompasses design, creation, organization, management, retrieval, analysis dissemination, visualization, and use of chemical information”

Thus the field of Chemoinformatics was never founded, nor was it formally installed. It gradually evolved.

Chemical databases

Many institutions maintain their own databases of chemical compounds. Some of these databases are accessible to public, however some are proprietary. The number of compounds in each database varies from several hundred thousand to even millions. Anyone can search these databases for compounds of his/her interest and get the result in seconds. There are databases for *virtual molecules* also i.e. such compounds which do not exist but can be synthesized using conventional methods of synthesis and quite often combinatorial chemistry techniques. The size of these databases often runs into billions of structures.

The question is how the information about a chemical structure can be stored in a computer? Popular programs like ChemDraw or ISIS/Draw are available for chemists to draw 2D structures for publications or presentations. One possible solution would be to save the structure in database as an image obtained by scanning a print of the structure or in a text format as pdf (Portable Document Format). However, the image file is not of real value for storage, since it occupies lot of space and is not appropriate for retrieval and search. Various ways (formats) have been developed to store structures in databases e.g.,

- (1) Molecular graphs
- (2) Connection tables
- (3) Linear notations (SMILES strings)

1. Molecular graphs

Graph theory is an established area of mathematics which has found great applications in computer science. A graph is an abstract structure containing nodes connected by edges, nodes representing atoms and edges representing bonds in a chemical structure². The nodes and edges have their own properties e.g. atomic number or atom type may be associated with each node and bond order may be associated with each edge. Molecular graphs for some compounds e.g. aspirin, cyclobutane, phosphorus (P_4) and 2,3,4,6-tetramethyl octane are shown below (clockwise) in Fig. 2. In case of aspirin the solid nodes represent oxygen atoms and the graph for benzene is the subgraph (subset) of the graph of aspirin. Acyclic molecules are generally represented using trees. A tree is a special type of graph which has a single path connecting each pair of vertices i.e. there is no ring within the graph. The root node of the tree is the starting point, the other vertices are either branch nodes or leaf nodes. In case of 2,3,4,6-tetramethyl octane C5 is the root node. The P_4 form of phosphorus is represented by a completely connected graph, in which all pairs of nodes are connected through an edge. Such graphs are rare in chemistry.

Fig. 2. Molecular graphs (clockwise from top left) of aspirin, cyclobutane, 2,3,4,6-tetramethyl octane and P_4 form of phosphorus [*An Introduction to Chemoinformatics* by Andrew R. Leach and V. J. Gillet].

There are certain limitations in representing chemical structures as molecular graphs. A graph represents only the topology of the molecule i.e. the way atoms are connected, thus can be drawn in many different ways

and may not be the standard representation of a chemical diagram. The question then arises i.e. how to determine whether two graphs are identical? A basic requirement is that the two graphs must have same number of nodes and edges followed by mapping to ascertain that each node and edge in one is equivalent to its counterpart in the other. There are well known algorithms in computer science which can establish this identity between two graphs. This phenomenon is known as “Graph isomorphism”^{3,4}.

2. Connection tables

Communication of a molecular graph to and from a computer can be carried out in several ways. A common means is to use a connection table. A simple connection table has two sections, first a list of atomic numbers of the atoms present in the molecule and second a list of bonds specified as pairs of bonded atoms. More details can be added to the connection tables e.g. the hybridization state of the atoms and bond orders. Information regarding the three coordinates, x, y and z of the atoms is also added which makes it much easier to produce the standard chemical drawing in 3D⁵. The connection tables are “hydrogen suppressed” i.e. hydrogen atoms are not shown but taken as implied. The connection table for aspirin is shown in Fig. 3, as developed by MDL Information Systems². Such a specific format can encode diverse information e.g. stereochemistry, isotopic data and electronic charge.

Linear notations

An alternative method for communicating molecular graph to and from computer is by using linear notation. In linear notation alphanumeric characters are used to encode molecular structures. Linear notations are more convenient and compact than connection tables, therefore more useful for storing and transmitting large number of molecules. Although Wiswesser line notation (WLN)^{6,7} initiated in 1949, reported in 1954 and developed in late 60's and was widely used but SMILES notation (Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry Specification)^{8,9} is much simpler and user friendly, therefore is more extensively used.

Few rules have to be followed to write SMILES strings. For creating a SMILES string one has to walk through the molecule in such a way that all the atoms are visited just once. SMILES format is hydrogen suppressed, hydrogen atoms are implied, however in exceptional cases these are added. Some of the rules are as follows,

the symbol @ e.g. the two isomers of alanine are written as, $N[C@H](C)C(=O)O$ and $N[C@@H](C)C(=O)O$. This is an exception where hydrogen atoms are indicated.

- (8) Geometrical isomerism (*cis-trans* or *E/Z*) about the double bonds is indicated by slashes e.g. *cis* butene is $C/C=C/C$ and *trans* butene is $C/C=C/C$.

Some examples are given here in order of increasing complexity of structure (Fig. 4).

Methane : C

Ethane : CC

2-Methyl pentane : CC(C)CCC

Acetic acid : CH_3COOH is $CC(=O)O$

Succinic acid : $HOOC-CH_2-CH_2-COOH$ is $OC(=O)CC(=O)O$

Aspirin : is $CC(=O)Oc1ccccc1C(=O)O$

Serotonin : is $NCCc1c(nH)c2ccc(O)cc12$

Progesterone : is $CC(=O)C1CCC2C3CCC4=CC(=O)CCC4(C)C3CCC12C$

Fig. 4. Examples of SMILES strings for some molecules.

Canonical representation of chemical structures

There may be different ways to represent the connection table or SMILES string for a given molecule. In connection table the atoms may be numbered in different ways and in SMILES string different sequences may be followed through the molecule e.g. aspirin may be written in many ways, two of which may be, OC(=O)c1ccccc1OC(=O)C and c1cccc(OC(=O)C)c1C(=O)O. Thus, for a molecule containing “n” atoms there can be n! different ways of numbering a connection table. To meet this problem, “**Canonical representation**” of the molecular structures is suggested. It is a unique ordering of the atoms for any molecular graph. Morgan algorithm (1965) has been developed for determining canonical order of atoms, in which “connectivity values” are calculated for differentiating atoms. The connectivity values for each atom of aspirin has been shown in Fig. 5. Initially each atom is assigned a connectivity value equal to the number of atoms attached to it. In the second and consecutive steps the connectivity values are changed according to the sum of the connectivity values of the connected atoms. This process is continued till the number

Fig. 5. Application of Morgan algorithm for constructing atomic connectivity values for aspirin molecule [*An Introduction to Chemoinformatics* by Andrew R. Leach and J. Gillet].

of connectivity values reaches a maximum. In case of aspirin initially there are only three values of connectivity i.e. 1, 2 and 3. In subsequent iterations it increases to 6, 8 and finally remains constant at 11. The atom with highest connectivity value is then chosen as the first atom in the connection table, its neighbors are then listed in order of their connectivity values, further their neighbours and so on. If a tie occurs the atomic numbers or bond orders are considered.

An algorithm "CANGEN" developed for SMILES strings is similar to Morgan algorithm. Canonical ordering of atoms is developed, which allows only one unique structure for each molecule e.g. aspirin can have only one canonical SMILES i.e. CC(=O)Oc1ccccc1C(=O)O.

Many other formats have been developed for representing molecules. IUPAC has devised canonical [IChI] and Chemical Markup Language (CML) is designed for transmitting information over internet.

Concluding remarks

Chemoinformatics has matured into a scientific discipline and has changed the way we perceive chemistry. The chemical industry and specifically pharmaceutical industry is today in dire need for specialists in chemoinformatics. There is need that chemoinformatics must be taught in academia, specifically by integrating it with regular chemistry courses.

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